

STAGES OF LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6629266>

Key words: preproduction, early production, speech emergence, intermediate fluency, advanced fluency.

After teachers have established a relationship with their ELL students by learning their names, it is time to assess learners for placement to determine where to begin.

Cummins (2001, 1981) concluded that it could take 2-5 years for ELL students to become conversationally adept, and it could take 5-10 years for those same students to become academically adept in a second language. Studies conducted by Krashen and Terrel (1983) explored the stages of language development for second language acquisition. Wes described the five stages of second-language acquisition as follows: preproduction, early production, speech emergence, intermediate fluency and advanced fluency.

Current research by Hill and Flynn (2006) continued to use the same stages of second language acquisition. According to research (Hill & Flynn; Krashen& Terrell), each of the five stages is evaluated by characteristics, approximate time frames, and teacher prompts. In the preproduction or silent period, the ELL student has few oral skills, and cannot understand, read or speak the targeted language. In addition, the ELL student will not be able to work independently nor have the ability to dramatize words, concepts, or events. By the end of the preproduction stage, the student will have some understanding of what is heard. The time frame for this stage is approximately 0-6 months.

During the early production stage, the ELL student's vocabulary will comprise one or two-word responses, present tense verbs, key words and phrases, and limited comprehension.

The second stage of language acquisition lasts approximately 6 months – 1 year. The third stage in language acquisition is the speech emergence stage and lasts from 1-3 years depending on the individual student's progress. Characteristics of this stage include improved comprehension, producing simple sentences, some understanding of jokes, and the making of grammar and pronunciation errors. The fourth stage can last from 3-5 years. During the intermediate fluency stage, the ELL student has improved comprehension to an excellent status and makes few grammatical errors.

The final stage is advanced fluency and the time frame is 5-7 years. During the final stage of language acquisition, the ELL student possesses near-native levels of speech. All students in the ESOL programs will progress through all five of the stages (Carrasquillo & Rodriguez, 1997).

The target language is almost always English for schools in Uzbekistan. It is important for educators to remember that the methods used in the classroom might need modifications to meet the ELL student's needs. To create an environment that will be comfortable for ELL students within the ESOL classroom and mainstreamed regular classroom, teachers must be flexible and understanding in order to have a positive influence on the ELL student's success. Creating the proper environment will be an ongoing process as daily problems surface. Some examples of daily divergences that could surface are conflicts with life styles, values, beliefs, and communication skills (Carrasquillo & Rodriguez, 1997). A growing challenge to all teachers in Uzbekistan educational system is teaching the English language to ELL students. It is no longer just the sole responsibility of the ESOL teacher, but is now the responsibility of all of the school staff.

According to data collected by Hill & Flynn (2006), not only are the public school systems facing greater numbers of ELL students, but the ELL population is the fastest growing segment of the overall school makeup. Recognizing and adapting to a student's unique learning style is one aspect of building that all-important relationship between student and teacher. With this in mind, teachers must read, listen, question, and observe closely to understand and help students convey what they want to say. People are different, and educators are made aware of this every day in hallways, cafeterias, classrooms, and playgrounds. All people, including educators, realize that people come in different sizes, shapes, intelligence levels, abilities, and talents. These varying qualities include different skin tones and cultures, and educators must adapt to meet the needs of all students regardless of their differences (Fitzgerald, 1999).

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